

MODERATING ROLE OF RESILIENCE: WHEN ABUSIVE SUPERVISION IMPACTS DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE AND EMPLOYEES' VOICE

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Received: 26.05.2019, Accepted: 17.09.2019

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the role played by abusive supervision in decreasing the voice of employees. This study tested the mediating role of distributive justice in the relationship between abusive supervision and employee's voice and moderating role of resilience in the relationship between abusive supervision and employee voice, and abusive supervision and distributive justice as well. A sample of 461 employees was contacted from 3S and 2S dealerships of automobiles sector of Pakistan. Using convenience sampling technique, data was collected through four structured questionnaires. Respondents duly filled in consent form for being participants of the study. To avoid variable biasedness Time Lag Technique was used for collecting data. Data Analyses were carried out by using SPSS and AMOS. Abusive supervision was found having negative impact on employees' voice. Perception of abusive supervision has a negative impact on perception of distributive justice which in turn decreases employees' voice. Resilience as a psychological resource has been found moderating the relationship between abusive supervision and employees' perception of distributive justice, and the relationship between abusive supervision and employees' voice. This study provides an insight to managers to figure out the adverse impact of abusive supervision on voice behaviors of employees. Abusive supervision works as a hurdle in voicing the silence of the subordinates. Managers, therefore, need to take measures for discouraging abusive supervision in the work place. An abuse free organizational environment will induce employees to give their much-needed feedback

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and opinion in the organizational matters. Moreover, managers need to find ways to develop resilience in the employees as resilience like other components of PsyCap is a state which can be developed and strengthened. The present study investigates the supervisor's abusive behavior to be an obstacle in voicing the silence of subordinates. It provides evidence that distributive justice mediates the relationship between abusive supervision and employees' voice behaviors. This study broadens the understanding that how abusive supervision leads to employees' voice behaviors through mediation of distributive justice, moreover, the mitigating role of resilience, (a component of Psychological Capital), has been emphasized in this study.

Key Words: Abusive supervision, Employees' Voice, Distributive Justice, Resilience

Introduction

Employee-organizational relationship is subject to a continuous change owing to the modern economic challenges based on cut-throat competition and characterized by technology and innovation (Baker et al., 2011). This changing relationship has brought the conventional concept of employee's performance into question. Modern day researchers are shifting their focus of studies from employee's proficiency to employee's level of commitment and engagement (Griffin et al., 2007). Employee performance is multifaceted which comprises of within-role, extra-role and anti-role behaviors (Wallace, E., Chernatony L. de., Buil, I., 2011). All these behaviors are important but extra-role behaviors, being positive role behaviors, are what modern day employers seek to enhance.

Drawing from the literature on positive psychology, positive organizational behaviors (POB) have been defined as "the study and application of positively oriented human resource strengths and psychological capacities that can be measured, developed, and effectively managed for performance improvement" (Luthans, 2002, p. 59; Nelson & Cooper, 2007; Turner, Barling, & Zaharatos, 2002; Wright, 2003).

Katz in 1964 introduced the concept of extra-role behaviors. Smith et al., (1983) termed these behaviors as Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCB), Mackenzie et al., (1993) considered OCB as discretionary and Organ (1988) argued that these behaviors are not recognized by formal reward system though such behaviors are important in promoting organizational effectiveness. Morison (2014) termed voice and silent behaviors of employees as extra-role discretionary behaviors.

Voice is giving feedback and opinion in the organizational matters and silence is withholding of voice, not giving feedback or opinion or even not reporting issues related to co-workers or any organizational activities.

Employees mostly face an internal conflict of either sharing their ideas and reservations or to keep silent, and in most cases silence wins; whereas speaking up is beneficial and silence can be very harmful for both employees and organizations (Morrison, 2014). A silent climate is an obstacle in the way of achieving organizational outcomes (Organ, 2013). Consequences of a silent climate can be very grave if seen in the organizational context. Employees' performance and dedication may decrease with an increase in turnover intention and overall dissatisfaction (Morrison, 2014). On the other hand, voice is a channel used by subordinates to have their say in the organizational matters; enhancing communication network that increases employees' engagement and performance (Armstrong, 2007; Newcomb, 2012). Wilkinson and Barry (2016) termed voice as a "mechanism for productive cooperation" that paves the path for the long-term sustainability of the firm and it also ensures economic well-being of the workers. Employees being vocal means they exist in the organization and if they are silent i.e. don't report work issues with fellow workers, or don't show dissatisfaction towards unwanted managerial decisions, means they don't exist in the organization (Donaghey et al., 2011; Wilkinson et al., 2014). An environment, that favors the voice raised by employees, takes organizations to success whereas, a silent climate can cause organizational failure (Emelifeonwu & Valk, 2019).

The antecedents of this silent environment can be many but one of the factors can be supervisor's attitude to be abusive (Wang & Jiang, 2015). Tepper (2000) defined abusive supervision as employees' perceptions related to supervisor's continuous display of verbal or nonverbal hostile behaviors not including physical abuse. Robinson and Bennet (1995) call abusive supervision "a deviant organizational behavior". Ashforth (1997) termed it as "tyrannical" which includes "belittling subordinates, displaying little consideration and using noncontingent punishment". Abusive supervision can be costly for organizations if its psychological cost is estimated as it increases job dissatisfaction, emotional exhaustion, turnover and above all counterproductive behaviors (Martinko et al., 2013; Schyns & Schilling, 2013; Tepper, 2007). It is a great concern for the organizations today because role of supervision cannot be denied in shaping the subordinates' behaviors that surely leads to organizational effectiveness (Tariq & Ding,

2018). Morrison (2014) lists down negative impacts of abusive supervision on OCB, knowledge sharing, and psychological capital. Aryee et al., (2008) highlights negative impacts of abusive supervision on subordinates helping attitudes and organizational commitment. Being vocal to give feed-back, opinions, suggestions are among extra-role discretionary behaviors, however, on finding hostile attitude of the supervisor employees may withdraw their voice and become silent (Wang & Jiang 2015).

Constanze Eib (2015) highlighted the need of studying justice by considering the actors of justice (the authority figures supervisors, & managers.) who are responsible for keeping a just environment, e.g supervisor and managers. Extra-role behaviors may not be counted in the formal reward system, but they are affected by organizational reward (justice) policies (Omer & Umut, 2007). The perception of organizational justice enables employees to poise a positive approach. It helps them engage profoundly in their work and to live with a pride of being part of the organizational system (Crawshaw, Cropanzano, Bell, & Nadisic, 2013). Organizational justice can be an important element in predicting the supervisor-subordinate relationship, employee performance and other work-related attitudes (Cropanzano, Prehar, & Chen, 2002). Similarly, perception of workplace injustice tarnishes employees' self and social image (Greenberg, 1990) and leads to job dissatisfaction (Aquino, Griffeth, Allen & Hom, 1997). Perceived injustice which is produced by negative work experiences like abusive supervision may lead to employees' dissatisfied life (Tepper, 2000). Wang and Jiang (2015) have found out that abusive supervision gives rise to interactional injustice that produces a negative impact on employees' extra-role behaviors like prosocial voice and silence. Khalid M., Bashir S., Khan A. K., and Abbas N., (2018) have found the same negative impact of abusive supervision on employees' perception of interactional justice and its further impact on knowledge hiding behaviors. Zellars et al., (2002) found abusive supervision to be negatively affecting employees' perceptions of procedural and interpersonal justice. Tepper (2000) believed that facing an abusive supervisor subordinates may experience "relative deprivation" that according to justice theories may lead to the perception of distributive injustice. In previous studies, researchers have used Interactional justice as a mediator (Wang & Jiang 2015; Kim, Lee & Yun 2016; Maria et.al., 2018). Extending the body of knowledge in present study, distributive justice has been studied as a mediator in the relationship between abusive supervision and employees' voice.

Facing an abusive supervisor subordinates has to fight at two fronts; to manage relationship with the abusive supervisor and to check their own self from being falling into negative emotional state (Wang & Jiang, 2015). Managing both at the same time not only requires lot of energy but also a stable emotional state. This state can be maintained if subordinates have enough psychological resources, psychological strength and certain personality characteristics.

Resilience, one of the components of Psychological Capital (PsyCap) gives one the psychological strength to handle stress (Luthans et al., 2007). Psychological Capital (PsyCap) is a representation of positive psychological state and individual motivational propensities. This construct has four components namely, self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience (Luthans, Avolio, Avey & Norman, 2007). The construct of PsyCap are “state-like,” as compared to Big Five personality dimensions which is “trait-like” construct, which implies, PsyCap is not stable, rather it may be developed and changed, (though these states are not temporary) (Luthans et al 2007), Same has been supported by past research as well as theory building (Luthans, Avolio, Avey, & Norman 2007). PsyCap is conceptualized as a positive resource capacity builder (Luthans, 2002). It has been found to be related to positive work attitudes Luthans et al., (2010).

Present study has focused on the component of resilience, as it helps individuals “reacting positively to the setbacks” Luthans et al., (2010) and in the face of problematic situations and tough conditions resilience supports one to sustain and fight back and “even beyond to attain success” (Luthans et al., 2007, p3). Empirical studies found resilient subordinates more likely retain their emotional state than less resilient counterparts. The bouncing back after facing an abusive situation makes them stronger and more determined and readier for the next situation (Luthans et al., 2007). For resilient individuals, who react positively to setbacks, the impact of abusive supervision on employee voice may not be negative. Abusive supervision creates an adverse and stressful situation for employees at the work place, however, individuals with higher levels of resilience are more likely to withstand this stress, whereas individuals with lesser resilience are likely fall a prey to adversity. Resilience enables employees to see beyond failures and give their best performance even in most challenging and adverse circumstances. It is a sort of continuous process that every time when employees return to homeostasis after an adverse event they become more resolute and determined. Fredrickson and Joiner (2002) studied the

said states and termed them as “upward aspiring efforts”. Dejana., Tea., Ivanec and Miljevi, (2014) studied school teachers’ resilience.

Our study, therefore, focused on role of actor of justice (supervisor, the authority figures) in affecting the positive organizational behavior of employees, i.e. ‘employees’ voice’. Present study has investigated the mitigating role of resilience in the relationship between Abusive supervision and employee voice as well as abusive supervision and perception of distributive justice. Our study has focused on the antecedents of employee voice (positive organizational behavior) and the process through which abusive supervision affects this positive organizational behavior.

Theoretical Framework

Relationship between Abusive Supervision and Employee’s Voice

Hobfoll (2001)’s Conservation of Resource Theory (COR), as a stress theory, has been extensively utilized to understand workplace behaviors (Hobfoll et al., 2014); stress in family as well as at work, (Halbesleben, Harvey, & Bolino, 2009), burnout (Halbesleben, 2006) and Job control (Park, et al 2009). COR describes the motivation that drives humans to not only maintain their present resources but also accrue new resources (Hobfoll, 1989). According to COR, people try to protect and retain their acquired and accumulated resources (Hobfoll, 1989). Resources are the things valued by the individuals, these valued things may be specific objects, states, or conditions (Halbesleben, Paustian-Underdal, and Westman, 2014). Environment, personal characteristics to time, money, skills can also be the resources (Hobfoll, 2001). These resources are so much valued that anticipating loss of resources or when resources are actually lost, or after spending the resources one finds lack of gained resources (Halbesleben, 2014) is stressful (Hobfoll & Shirom, 2001). Hobfoll, (1989) stated that when facing lack of gained resources individuals are likely to make defensive efforts at conserving the remaining resources, these resources are important as with the help of these resources they try to achieve their goals. Halbesleben et al., (2014) call this behavior of saving from resource loss or to minimize the risk of loss, a motivational element. Although employees experienced hard time while attaining these resources, protecting the resources, but finding a threat or actually losing the resource is extremely stressful (Hobfoll, 2001). That’s why individuals try to avoid resource loss and engage in the behaviors that bring their resources to minimum risk of loss.

COR theory reflects that people devote their resources to avoid negative situations and stressful conditions. COR states that loss of any types of resources will drive individuals into certain levels of stress (Hobfoll, Stevan (1989). They try to build more resources and prevent themselves from any resource loss. This obtaining of resources increases their resources repository promising to attain further resources. Resources get amassed in “Resource Caravans” (Hobfoll, 2002). Two basic principles are to be considered in this regard; Primacy of Resource Loss and Resource Investment. Former principle states that losing resources is harmful for individuals, latter principle (Resource Investment of COR) states that people will tend to invest resources in order to protect against resource loss, to recover from losses, and to gain resources (Halbesleben et al 2014).In a workplace study, it was found that individuals are not sensitive to the resources they are receiving instead they are more concerned if the demands are increased (Lee, & Ashforth, 1996).

Abusive supervision, a severe occupational stressor (Tepper, 2001), may be perceived as a constant threat to resource loss like energy, motivation, dignity, safety and the like. (Tuckey & Neil, 2014). The situation worsens when the abuse is continuous, and the individual is threatened to a complete resource loss (Hobfoll & Shirmen, 2001). With decreasing resource, the threat to further loss becomes an alarming situation, that pushes an individual to a “loss spiral” endangering their abilities to cope up difficulties, motivation and overall well-being (Halbesleben & Bowler, 2007). Since the loss of resource is more prominent than the gain of a resource (Hobfoll, 2001) individuals facing abusive supervision tend to take a defensive position to prevent further loss or to conserve the remaining pool of resources (Xu et al., 2015). To safeguard one’s remaining resources by remaining silent and not raising voice to any issue or remaining concerned with one’s own business is perhaps a safe and a natural mode of conduct (Xu et al., 2015).

Drawing on COR theory, employee’s make deliberate decision of decreasing one’s voice and increasing silence as a shield for their remaining resources (Ng & Felfman, 2012). in this context sharing information with such supervisor, becomes a tough task, needing a lot of energy and it takes longer to share such information. Gathering energy for interacting an abusive supervisor, at times, delays the sharing of information, which delays the performance of daily operations. Studies have found adverse impact of supervisor’s negative behavior on the work outcomes. Wang & Jiang (2015) studied the impact of abusive

supervision to be negative on prosocial voice & silence, similarly, Alisher, Do, Jaehoon and Junghyun (2016) investigated the negative impact of authoritarian leadership on employee creativity. (Harris, Kacmar, and Zivnuska, (2007) stated that abusive supervision makes the employees more silent and the tendency to raise voice in the organization is decreased. Alisher, Do, Jaehoon and Junghyun (2016) highlighted that when employees find their leader or manager as authoritative and abusive they prefer holding back their suggestions in the work-related issues. Drawing on these studies, we hypothesize that:

H1. Perception of Abusive Supervision will negatively affect employees' voice.

Distributive Justice as Mediator

Martin (1981) stated that subordinates of an abusive supervisor feel to be at a disadvantage as compared to their peers when they find their supervisor belittling them instead of providing guidance. Tepper (1995) states that instead of berating the subordinates, the function of a supervisor is to mentor his/her subordinates for preparing them to meet future challenges. Abusive treatment by a supervisor can adversely influence the perceptions of inputs of subordinates that they use in assessing distributive justice. Theories explaining distributive justice suggest that individuals compare their inputs and outcomes with those of a referent (Adams & Yellen, 1976). The individuals having abusive supervisors feel deprived relatively to the referent (Martin, 1981). This deprivation leads them to feel that they are getting less than what they deserve than the referent group.

Working under abusive supervision is quite challenging for the employees, who have to overcome many hinderances and obstacles on daily basis, their energies are wasted in dealing with such supervision, as a result they need more energies to carry out their routine operations. One of the examples can be the stress of communicating to a supervisor, who is always prone to negative criticism instead of providing constructive feedback, ignoring the efforts put by the employees, this may produce unfair distributive justice perception among them (Zellar et al.,2002). Colloquitt (2001) defines distributive justice to be a comparison between the outcomes received against the efforts, performance and contributions made by the employee. The received outcomes are not only material rewards but also the behaviors and attitudes of their bosses. For example, if an employee is given material rewards along with a derogatory and demeaning attitude. This abusive attitude of a supervisor can trigger perceptions of distributive injustice among employees.

Perception of distributive justice tend to be negative even if material reward is followed by negative or derogatory and demeaning attitude. This perception may lead the employees to negative organizational behavior (instead of positive organizational behavior) this negative organizational behavior in turn affects organizational outcomes in the long run. Reaction to perception of inequity may result in anger, damage to self-esteem, desire for holding back (Aryee, Chen, Sun & Debrah, 2007). The negative impact of abusive supervision over employees' voice behavior is mediated by justice perceptions of employees (Wang & Jiang, 2015), especially distributive justice (Tepper, 2007; Aryee, Chen, Sun & Debrah, 2007).

In the same vein it is hypothesized in present study that the perception of unjust distribution can make subordinates less vocal. Therefore, it is hypothesized thus:

H2. Perception of distributive justice will mediate the relationship between Abusive supervision and Employees' voice in such a way that abusive supervision will negatively affect perception of distributive justice that will in turn decrease employees' voice behavior.

Resilience as Moderator:

Resilience can be explained best with the help of COR theory (Hobfoll, 2002). Drawing on COR theory, individuals try their level best to protect resilience, a psychological resource moreover. Factors in the organization that threaten to negatively impact this resource are dealt with effort, for example, when faced with the abusive supervision, a major workplace stressor (Tepper, 2001), employees feel that their resilience is ending, they put their maximum efforts to retain this resource. Workplace stressor, the threatening environment in the organization characterized by abusive supervision, can make resilient people more resilient. Resilience enables the employee to perform and succeed at a challenging task with confidence. It enables one to not only succeed at present but also in future and in times of adversity sustaining and bouncing back with successful efforts (Luthans et al., 2006). With bouncing back, individuals start attaining their lost resources back or even build up new ones. With every challenge met, every difficulty passed, and every stressful event faced resilient workers become more resilient than before.

The bouncing back from every adversity and stress makes resilient individual to cope adverse situations successfully. Smith et al., (2008) calls resilience to recover from stress and every new recovery makes the

resilient more immune to the new stress situation. This immunity makes resilient individuals feel less stressed in the adverse situations than the individuals with low resilience (Connor & Davidson, 2003). Instead of feeling stressed and outcast, resilient individuals flourish in the times of adversity that may be caused by feeling of increased responsibility (Christensen & Knardahl 2010).

For the resilient employees the impact of abusive supervision on employee's voice may be contrary. The adverse situation created by abusive supervision may make resilient individuals thrive and their voice may not be affected so badly as in case of lesser resilient individuals. Instead of fearing a resource loss, they may perceive it as an opportunity to increase resilience as a resource (Halbesleben et al., 2014) and instead of going numb they may raise voice. In other words, the relationship between abusive supervision and employee's voice, will be lesser negative for individuals having higher levels of resilience than the individuals having lower levels of resilience. In this vein, we hypothesized that:

H3. The relationship between abusive supervision and employees' voice will be moderated by resilience in a way that this relationship will be weaker for higher levels of resilience and stronger for lower levels of resilience.

Empirical studies found resilient employees maintaining their health, performance, and happiness even while facing adverse workplace stressors like experiencing stressor like downsizing (Maddi, 1987). Luthans et al. (2005) found a significant relationship between the performance of employees and change/transformation. Larson and Luthans (2006) found resilient employees scoring high on job satisfaction. Similarly, in another study employees' level of resilience was found to be significantly related to employees' commitment, satisfaction and happiness (Youssef & Luthans 2007). In the same vein it may be hypothesized that Impacts of Abusive supervision on employees' perception of distributive justice can be moderated under the influence of resilience.

H4. Resilience will moderate the relationship between abusive supervision and distributive justice in such a way that this negative relationship will be weakened for higher levels of resilience and strengthened for lower levels of resilience.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework:

Research Methodology

Research Design

This study was carried out in the field setting, unit of analysis for the study is individual, as employees were asked to fill in the research questionnaire individually. Data was collected using time lag technique as suggested by Podsakoff et al., (2003). A temporal separation of two weeks was created between the IV and DVs to evade common method bias. At first the respondents were asked to rate abusive supervision, resilience and fill in the demographic information and after fifteen days rest of the variables of the study were asked to be rated.

Participants and Procedure

Present research measured the responses of regular working employees of 3S and 2S dealerships of Automobiles Sector of Pakistan. These dealerships have proper pay structures, their employees were regular working employees with a career path in the industry. These dealerships are well scattered throughout the country. Convenience sampling technique has been used. Data was collected from the cities that are considered good for business in automobiles sector. Questionnaires filled by respondents from the Punjab, KPK and AJ&K Karachi and Quetta regions. Respondents from Punjab, KPK and AJ&K were distributed in one-to one interaction, whereas, questionnaires were mailed to the respondents from Karachi and Quetta.

For calculating the sample size, the equation 1 for determining the sample size when the population is unknown presented by Glenn D.

Israel (1992) and endorsed by Sekaran (2006) was used. This equation calculated the sample size to be 382 as enough to carry out the study.

Respondents were approached in their natural work settings without disturbing their routine operations. Before asking them to be participants of the present study, respondents were informed about the purpose of the research. Participants were informed about their rights (as per APA ethical codes) including their right to withdraw from the research in case they find themselves unwilling to continue being part of the research. Respondents gave their informed consent to join the research.

A total no of 510 questionnaires have been distributed. Only 49 of the questionnaires have been returned incomplete or not returned at all. Thus, providing the researcher with the response rate of 90.3 % leaving 461 responses valid for data analysis. 90.7% responses were taken from male respondents and 9.3% are taken from female respondents.

After collection of data all the questionnaires were thoroughly checked for correction of errors to ensure highest standards of quality of data (Cooper and Emory, 1995). All questionnaires were coded and then entered in the SPSS for further analyses.

Measures

All the scales for the variables of the study are adopted. For these scales Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was tested/checked with the help of SPSS.

For present study, we utilized following four scales. Abusive Supervision scale was measured using 15-items scale developed by Tepper (2001). For present study, the Cronbach's Alpha for Abusive supervision is calculated to be .91. Employee voice was measured by using the 5-items scale by Omer (2009). The Cronbach's Alpha value for employee voice for present study is .84. or measuring distributive justice, sub scale of distributive justice from organizational justice fscale (Colquitt 2001) was used. The Cronbach's Alpha calculated for distributive justice is .839. Resilience was measured with the help of six items sub scale adopted from PsyCap scale (Luthans et al. 2007). In the present study. Cronbach's Alpha value for resilience is .870. The values of Cronbach's alpha of all scales in this study indicate that the scales used in the instrument are suitable for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 below represents mean, standard deviation and correlation for the variables of this study. All the study variables are found to be positively and significantly correlated with each other. Abusive supervision is positively related to employees' voice ($r = .113$, $p < 0.05$) as well as with distributive justice ($r = .359$, $p < 0.01$) and resilience ($r = .698$, $p < 0.01$). There is not a single highly or perfect correlation which may cause problem in further analysis.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation and Corelation Coefficients among study variables (N=461)

S.No		Mean	S.D	1	2	3	4
1	Abu_Sup	4.03	1.67	1			
2	Dist_just	3.51	1.06	.36**	1		
3	Emp_Voice	3.61	1.08	.11*	.18**	1	
4	Resilience	3.95	1.39	.69**	.39**	.26**	1

Note: Abu_sup = abusive supervision, Dist_just is distributive justice, emp_voice+employee voice

***.* Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Hypotheses Testing

In the table:2 Abusive Supervision is explaining 2.8% of the variance in explaining Employee's Voice ($R^2 = 0.023$). This Adjusted R-square value is explaining variance percent in the employee voice (dependent variable) that is accounted for by variations in the scores of abusive supervision (independent variable). In present study, fitness of the model is depicted by the F value in the model which is greater than 4 and significant at less than 0.05 (the lower the better). In present analysis, Abusive Supervision is a negative and significant predictor of Employee Voice ($\beta = -0.13$; $p = 0.000$). Data in the present study is supporting our hypothesis 1.

Table 2: Linear Regression for Abusive Supervision and Employee Voice

Model		B	SE	B	T	P
1	(Constant)	4.36	.15		29.43	.000
	Abusive Supervision	-.13	.03	-.17	-3.65	.000

R²= 0.028; F= 13.34; p<0.000

Mediation Analyses

For testing mediation following criteria was used. Some form of mediation (or partial mediation) is supported if the effect of M (path b) remains significant after controlling for X. If X is no longer significant when M is controlled, the finding supports full mediation. If X is still significant (i.e. X and M both significantly predict Y), the finding supports partial mediation (Baron & Kenny, 1989; MacKinnon, Fairchild, & Fritz, 2007; Hayes, 2013).

Table 3: Distributive Justice as Mediator in the relationship between Abusive Supervision and Employee's Voice

	Dist Jus (M1)			EmpVoice (Y)		
	Coef	SE	P	Coef	SE	P
Abu_Sup (X)	.31	.04	.000	-.26	.05	.000
M1	-	-	-	.15	.06	.008
Constant	2.19	.16	.000	4.05	.29	.000
	Model 1			Model 2		
	R ² = .129			R ² = .066		
	F = 67.75			F = 6.431		
	P = .000			P = .000		

Note: Abu_sup = abusive supervision, Dist_just = distributive justice, emp_voice =employee voice

The results show that Abusive Supervision (independent variable) has significant impact on the distributive justice (mediator) (Coeff. 0.31, $p < 0.05$) as well as on employee's voice (dependent variable) (Coeff. -0.26, $p < 0.05$). While in model 1 it is shown that $R^2 = 0.129$, $F = 67.75$, $p = 0.000$ and model 2 $R^2 = 0.066$, $F = 6.431$, $p = 0.000$. The model fit summary R^2 , F value and p value are also showing significant effect of mediating variable except model 2 because R^2 value is very low, F value is also less than 3.96 (accepted value) and p value is greater than 0.05.

In present study, for some form of mediation (or partial mediation) is supported if the effect of M (path b) remains significant after controlling for X. If X is no longer significant when M is controlled, the finding supports full mediation. If X is still significant (i.e. X and M both significantly predict Y), the finding supports partial mediation (Baron & Kenny, 1989; MacKinnon, Fairchild, & Fritz, 2007; Hayes, 2013).

So, we can conclude that our findings support mediation of distributive justice between abusive supervision and employee voice hypothesis H2 stands as accepted.

Moderation Analyses

For testing moderation effects (H3) following analysis was conducted.

Table 4: Resilience as moderator in the Relationship between Abusive Supervision and Employee Voice

Model Summary						
	R	R-sq	F	df1	df2	p
	.3138	.0985	16.6404	3.000	457.000	.000
Model						
		coeff	SE	t		p
constant		0.336	.678	.4963		.6199
Resilience (M)		.759	.194	3.9004		.000
AbuSup (X)		.489	.166	2.9434		.0003
int_1		-.116	.045	-2.5581		.010
Interactions: int_1 = AbuSup x Resilience						
Outcome Variable: EmpVoice (Y)						

Note: Abu_sup = abusive supervision, Emp_voice = employee voice

The results show Abusive Supervision (X) having significant positive impact on Employee Voice (Y) (Coeff. 0.489, $p < 0.05$). Resilience (M) is significantly predicting Employee Voice (Y) (Coeff. 0.759, $p < 0.05$) moreover, the Interaction term (Abusive supervision x Resilience) is also significantly predicting the employee's voice (Coeff. -0.116, $p < 0.05$), thus supporting our hypothesis 3 that anticipated moderating role of resilience in the relationship between abusive supervision and employee's voice.

Table 5: Resilience as moderator Over the Relationship between Abusive Supervision and Organizational justice Distributive

Model Summary					
R	R-sq	F	df1	df2	p
.352	.124	21.593	3.000	457.000	.000

Model	coeff	SE	t	p
constant	7.286	.728	9.996	.000
Resilience	-.682	.209	-3.266	.001
AbuSup	-.085	.178	-6.074	.000
int_1	.231	.049	4.707	.000

Interactions: int_1 = AbuSup x Resilience

Outcome Variable: dist_justice (Y)

Note: Abu_sup = abusive supervision, Dist_just = distributive justice

The results of Abusive Supervision (X) shows significant relationship with Organizational Justice Distributive (Y) (Coeff. -0.085, $p < 0.05$). Resilience (M) and Organizational Justice Distributive (Y) has significant relationship (Coeff. -0.682, $p < 0.05$) and Interaction term (AbuSup x Resilience) is significant (Coeff. 0.231, $p < 0.05$). Interaction term is significant ($p < 0.05$) depicting moderating role of resilience in the relationship between abusive supervision and distributive justice, therefore, supporting our Hypothesis (H4).

Discussions

Present study investigated the negative impact of abusive supervision on employees' voice. Mediating impact of distributive justice in the relationship between abusive supervision and employee's voice was assessed. Moreover, moderating role played by resilience was investigated in the relationship between abusive supervision and

distributive justice, as well as between abusive supervision and employees' voice. Present study tested four hypotheses to meet objectives of this study. All the hypotheses were supported by the data of this study. It was found out that abusive supervision significantly decreases employees' voice and this relationship is mediated by distributive justice. However, same does not hold true for the employees with higher levels of resilience.

The reason for the decrease in voice behavior under the impact of abusive supervision can be, as explained by COR theory, the conservation of further resource loss. Supervisors being in authority and position can damage the career or growth of an employee who directly confronts them, this being particularly true in case of Asian cultures (Wang & Jiang, 2015) because in Asian culture subordinates' achievements of goals and growth are linked with the approvals of their supervisors (Emerson, 1962). To conserve their resources, subordinates are less likely to confront their abusive supervisors that strengthens the negative relationship between abusive supervision and employee's voice behavior. The only response subordinates are left with is to withdraw extra-role behaviors such as voicing in the organization or co-workers related issues (Aquino, Tripp, & Bies, 2001).

The role played by organizational justice in defining employees' behaviors have been studied thoroughly by many researchers in the past. It encourages employees to predict their future with the organization and provides them with the basis to work for organizational effectiveness (Crawshaw, Cropanzano, Bell, & Nadisic, 2013; Cropanzano, Byrne, Bobocel, & Rupp, 2001). It is also a fact that enacting justice becomes difficult in certain situations and for certain individuals. The managers who enact fairness are of stable personalities and characteristics such as caring attitude and moral obligation to treat subordinates like they treat themselves (Brebels, De Cremer, Van Dijke, & Van Hiel, 2011; Patient & Skarlicki, 2010). Abusive supervisors display attitudes that are not caring and that is far away from moral obligations to treat subordinates as they treat themselves (Tepper, 2000). Abusive supervisor can be termed as injustice actor rather than a justice actor. It implies that he enhances injustice perceptions of employees resulting in negative consequences. Distributive justice is important when employees draw a comparison between them and a referent group, while facing an abusive supervisor. Abusive supervision decreases the sense of distributive justice of subordinates (Martin, 1981; Tepper, 2000) that negatively impacts work-

related outcomes like employees' prosocial voice and silence (Wang & Jiang, 2015).

Abusive supervision is a severe workplace stressor (faced by employees in an organization (Tepper, 2001). So, if employees are resilient the adverse effects of abusive supervision can be averted rather abusive supervision will make them more resilient and maintain a positive attitude. Fredrickson et al., (2008) stated that resilience makes employees more proactive in facing the adversity. It lessens the tensions and decreases the stresses caused by adverse environment. This managing stressful situation is due to utilization of their psychological resources. Number of empirical studies has established that positive role of resilience in organizational settings, e.g resilience behaviors affect positively to employees' work performance (Luthans et al., 2007) positive work attitudes (Youssef & Luthans, 2007), job satisfaction (Youssef & Luthans, 2007), reduced psychological distress (Utsey et al., 2008) and organizational commitment (Youssef & Luthans, 2007). Karatepe and Karadas (2015) found that employees having higher PsyCap are more satisfied with their profession and life than those having lower PsyCap.

Implications for Theory, Research and Practice

Present study has enhanced body of the knowledge in several ways. Employees' voice as a discretionary behavior has been studied and the impact of abusive supervision on employee's voice was investigated, thus strengthening our concept about negative consequences of abusive supervision.

Supervisors and managers need to realize that modern day organizations are run by both subordinates and leaders equally. Today's business environment is also featured by employees' feed-back to guarantee organizational smooth functioning and an effective decision-making process. Employees need to be motivated to pour in their thoughts and give their suggestions (Morrison & Milliken, 2003).

In the light of present research organizations may need to focus on building and improving upon resilience considering its positive role in employee's voice. Resilience, a component of state-like construct can be developed, for the improvement of work performance (Luthans, Avolio, Avey, & Norman 2007). Organizations may develop related intervention strategies. Developmental intervention based on resilience strategies has been discussed extensively by Masten and Reed (2002). Positive psychologist Csikszentmihalyi (as quoted in Kersting, 2003, p. 26) noted that such psychological capital "is developed through

a pattern of investment of psychic resources that results in obtaining experiential rewards from the present moment while also increasing the likelihood of future benefit”.

Employees’ voice and silence are important for organizations to compete in the cut-throat competitive business environment (Wang and Jiang, 2015). Organizations also need to put efforts in encouraging employees’ voice, a positive organizational behavior. Moreover, organizations in general and managers in particular need to discourage organizational factors e.g. abusive supervision that has been found playing a key role in discouraging employee’s voice. Development of positive organizational behavior is a positive approach to develop and manage human resources in the workplace (Luthans & Youssef, 2007; Luthans, Youssef, & Avolio, 2007).

Present study suggests two remedies to cure silent environment and turn it into a feed-back providing environment. First subordinates’ going numb and not providing feed-back is a consequence of abusive supervision, which must be discouraged. There should be a proper mechanism to check abusive behavior of the supervisor rather a system must be established for ensuring strict adherence to psychological safety of the subordinates (Robinson & O’Leary-Kelly, 1998). Perceptions of distributive justice are negatively impacted by abusive supervision. Supervisors need to pay due attention to elevate the spirit of employees by treating them with respect and care and this can only be done by reducing abusive behaviors. More distributive justice must be performed to shed the negative impacts of abusive supervision (Camps, Decoster, & Stouten, 2012).

Findings of present study supported the relationship between abusive supervision and employee voice behavior, the mediating role of distributive justice and moderating role of resilience in the relationship between abusive supervision and distributive justice. Abusive supervision was found negatively affecting the employee’s voice through the distributive justice. Moderating role of resilience was found between abusive supervision and employees’ voice.

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